

Analysis of the Effect of Product and Service Quality, *Electronic Word Of Mouth* (E-Wom), Brand Image and Perceived Customer Value on Repurchase Intention Through *Coffee-to-Go Shop* Customer Satisfaction in Generation Y and Generation Z in Jakarta During The Covid 19 Pandemic.

Maria Yosephine Elivia KI
Master of Management, Faculty of
Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University Jakarta, Indonesia

Sri Hartono
Master of Management, Faculty of
Economics and Business
Mercu Buana University Jakarta, Indonesia

Abstract:- The spread of the COVID-19 virus occurs almost all over the world and WHO has declared this period as a global pandemic. The existence of the COVID-19 pandemic has brought Indonesia close to the brink of recession, which has led to a decrease in consumption and purchasing power of the Indonesian people. But in fact, the local ready-to-drink coffee business is growing well and promising. This study aims to analyze the effect of product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth* (E-WOM), brand image and perceived customer value on repurchase interest through *coffee-to-go shop* customer satisfaction in Generation Y and Generation Z in DKI Jakarta. Sampling was conducted on 290 respondents consisting of 145 Generation Y respondents and 145 Generation Z respondents. The results of hypothesis testing concluded that Product and Service Quality, E-WOM, Brand Image, and Perceived Customer Value all have a positive and significant influence on Customer Satisfaction. Customer Satisfaction in this case also has a positive and significant influence on Repurchase Interest. For theoretical and practical implications, future researchers need to test

Repurchase Interest with other variables.

Keywords:- Product and Service Quality, E-WOM, Brand Image, Perceived Customer Value, Customer Satisfaction, Repurchase Intention.

I. INTRODUCTION

The 2019 Covid pandemic has had a huge impact on many aspects of people's lives, especially on the economy. Not only affecting the micro economy, the pandemic has affected the national economy. The government has created many regulations that limit the movement and activities of the community. This affects productivity and has a direct impact on labor.

Furthermore, from the consumer side, the pandemic has made a decrease in consumption and purchasing power of the Indonesian people according to McKinsey & Company research (2020) with 570 Indonesian respondents aged 18-65 years, it was found that there was a 5% decrease in the *beverages* consumption sector.

Table 1 Growth in Consumption of Daily Necessities Products During COVID-19 Konsumsi Ketika Situasi COVID-19 VS Sebelumnya (% Responden Yang Beli Setiap Produk)

Konsumsi Produk	Naik Signifikan (+20% atau lebih)	Naik (+5% sampai 20%)	Tidak ada perubahan	Turun (-5% sampai -20%)	Turun Signifikan (-20% atau lebih)	Net Inflow
Kesehatan	39	37	17	4	3	0%
Buah segar	31	37	21	7	3	0%
Rumah Tangga	28	37	27	5	3	0%
Personal Care	27	36	28	6	4	-1%
Telur	24	36	32	7	2	0%
Barang Kertas Rumah Tangga	20	37	37	5	2	0%
Air dalam Botol	24	31	35	7	3	-4%
Susu	20	35	32	9	5	-3%
Makanan dalam kemasan	19	30	33	12	6	-4%
Bayi	18	27	43	6	5	-1%
Makanan Beku	15	26	33	16	10	-4%
Makanan Ringan	14	26	37	16	6	-2%
Minuman	16	23	38	15	9	-5%
Makanan Deli	14	23	36	16	11	-4%
Perawatan Hewan Peliharaan	14	22	42	16	7	-2%
Bir	12	19	31	20	18	-4%
Minuman non alkohol	12	15	38	18	16	-4%
Makan cepat saji	11	14	33	29	12	-8%

Net inflow dihitung dengan mengurangi persentase responden membeli produk ketika pandemi dengan sebelum pandemi
 Source: Mckinsey & Company (2020)

One of the food and beverage industries affected by the COVID-19 pandemic is the coffee industry. Where in the figure below, it can be seen that there is a downward trend where the highest trend occurred in 2018 then fell from 2019 to 2021 during the COVID-19 pandemic to less than 6% (Ministry of Agriculture, 2018).

Fig 1 National Coffee Consumption 2016-2021
 Source: Ministry of Agriculture (2018)

But in fact, the local ready-to-drink coffee business is growing well and promising. Based on Statista data (2020b), there is a CAGR growth per 3 years, namely 2018-2020 and 2015-2017 for the *Ready to Drink (RTD) Coffee* market coverage. In 2018-2020 there was a CAGR growth of 32%, compared to 2015-2017 which only amounted to 26% (table 1.4).

Market Size Kopi Ready-to-Drink (RTD) di Indonesia dari 2011 hingga 2020

(dalam juta liter)

Fig 2 Market Size of RTD Coffee in Indonesia 2011-2020
Source: Statista (2020b)

Coffee-to-go-shop is the latest innovative concept and means the purchase of coffee that can be directly *picked up* without the need to wait long or without stopping at the *coffee shop*. Consumers can buy coffee by making independent *pick-ups* or using the help of online motorcycle taxis such as *gofood* or *grabfood*. According to data from Statista (2020a) "*Most Frequented Types Of Coffee Shops In The Previous Year Among Respondents In Indonesia As At October 2019*", it can be seen that 39 percent of Indonesian respondents stated that they preferred buying *coffee* from *coffee-to-go* shops compared to the previous year.

Fig 3 Types of Coffee Shops Preferred for Buying Indonesian Coffee 2019
Source: Statista (2020a)

In addition to growth in terms of market coverage, there is also a trend of growth in *Coffee Shop outlets* in Indonesia. Where based on Toffin data (2020) in 2019 there were 2937 *Coffee Shop outlets* in Indonesia which grew almost 3 times from 2016 which was only 1083 outlets. The data shows that there are several *coffee-to-go shop* brands that have a large number of outlets with national coverage, namely, Janji Jiwa, Kopi Kulo, Kopi Kenangan, Kopi Soe and Fore.

Table 2 Number of Coffee Shop Outlets in Indonesia Jumlah Gerai Coffee Shop di Indonesia pada 2019

Brand	Pembukaan Pertama	Jumlah Gerai
Anomali	2007	13
Bakoel Koffie	2001	2
Bhumi Kopi	2017	2
Coffee Bean	2001	108
Coffee Toffee	2006	100
Common Grounds	2013	8
Djournal Coffee	2013	21
Dunkin	1985	200
Excelso	1991	126
Filosofi Kopi	2015	3
First Crack	2012	4
Fore	2018	100
Harvest	2004	66
Janji Jiwa	2018	500
Jco Donut & Coffee	2005	273
Kopi Kecil	2016	6
Kopi Kenangan	2017	175
Kopi Soe	2017	150
Kulo	2018	300
Maxx Coffee	2015	74
McCafe	2005	40
Olala Cafe	1990	16
Ombe Kofie	2015	6
Segafredo Zenneti	2002	3
Starbucks	2002	421
Tahta Coffee	2019	7
Tanamera	2013	13
The Gade Coffee & Gold	2018	34
Tuku	2014	7
Upnormal Coffee Roaster	2016	20
Warunk Upnormal	2014	87
Kopitiam		42
Coffee Shops milik selebriti		10

Source: Toffin (2020)

Furthermore, based on M2Insight Market Research Indonesia data (M2Insights, November 2020), there are 8 large national coffee *shops* that experienced growth in 2020, where in this case there are 4 national *coffee-to-go shop* brands that are stable to survive and grow, namely Janji Jiwa, Kopi Kenangan, Kopi Kulo and Fore.

Table 3 Number of Outlets and Coverage of Coffee Shops in Indonesia

Brand	Pembukaan Pertama	Jumlah Gerai dan Coverage
Janji Jiwa	2018	800 di 50 kota (April 2020)
Starbucks	2002	440 di 25 kota (Februari 2020)
Kopi Kenangan	2017	400 (akhir 2020)
Kulo	2017	300 (Februari 2020)
Excelso	1991	126 (Agustus 2019)
Fore	2018	117 (April 2020)
Maxx Coffee	2015	83 di 23 kota (April 2019)
Flash Coffee	2019	8 di Jakarta, Singapore, Bangkok

Source: M2Insights (2020)

The fourth *coffee-to-go shop* in addition to having a large number of outlets, also has a high *brand WOM* based on the i-Buzz Asia survey (2020). Based on an i-Buzz Asia survey that looked at 70 coffee brands in Indonesia, including global and local brands. The survey found a total of 4,018 WOMs in a one-year period (July 2019 - June 2020) and a total of 3,052 WOMs for the top ten brands.

In terms of lifestyle, DKI Jakarta residents have the highest habit of consuming an average of 1-3 cups of coffee per day compared to other provinces based on research conducted by the HonestDocs Team in 2019 on 9,684 respondents aged 18-34 years from all over Indonesia. Both Generation Y and Generation Z are generations that dominate demographically, namely Generation Y (25-39 years old) of 2,671,104 residents and Generation Z (20-24 years old) of 818,069 residents with a total of 3,489,173 residents in Jakarta (BPS, 2021c).

After reviewing journals from several previous studies on repurchase interest, it is known that there are factors that influence repurchase interest, including according to Arlanda and Suroso (2018), it is known that *product and service quality has a positive and significant effect on repurchase interest through customer satisfaction*. According to Ratasuk and Gajesanand (2020), *brand image also directly has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention*. Then according to Muhajir and Indarwati (2021), *perceived customer value has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction*.

In addition, research by Santi and Suasana (2021) regarding electronic word-of-mouth (E-WOM) has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction. Through several research journals that have been reviewed, the authors found the variables in the study in the research of Gumilang, Yuliati, and Indrawan (2021). However, this study apparently has not examined the variable perception of customer value as one of the factors that influence repurchase interest through customer satisfaction. Then in other research journals, no research has been found that uses the variable of perceived customer value together with variables of product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth* (E-WOM) and brand image on repurchase intention through customer satisfaction, especially in terms of the *coffee-to-go shop* industry.

Based on the various background factors, phenomena and *research gaps* described, the authors chose to conduct a study that aims to determine the effect of product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth* (E-WOM), brand image and perceived customer value on repurchase interest through customer satisfaction in generation Y and generation Z *coffee-to-go shop* customers in DKI Jakarta during the COVID 19 pandemic.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Product and Service Quality

Product has the meaning of something that can be offered to the market to get attention, purchase, use or consumption that can fulfill needs (Wibisono, 2019). Products can be said to be one of the first and main marketing elements. Kotler and Armstrong (2018) emphasize that a product is something that can be offered to the market, gets attention, can be obtained, and can satisfy someone's wants or needs. According to Garvin (1987) to determine the dimensions of product quality, it can be through eight dimensions as described below:

- Performance, which is the performance of the main operations of a core product, such as the taste of coffee, the quality of raw materials, and the hygiene of coffee in a coffee-to-go shop that is good for customers to consume.
- Features, which are special characteristics or additional features of the product, such as the specialty of coffee products at coffee-to-go shops that distinguish them from coffee elsewhere.
- Reliability, namely the reliability of the product, such as the quality of coffee products at coffee-to-go shops can be relied on by customers.
- Comformance, namely the suitability of the product to its specifications, such as the suitability of coffee products at coffee-to-go shops with what customers expect.
- Durability, namely product durability, such as the ability of coffee products in coffee-to-go shops both in taste and packaging that are well maintained.
- Serviceability, which includes speed, competence, comfort, ease of repair services, and handling complaints, such as good service capabilities at coffee-to-go shops.
- Aesthetic, which is the attractiveness of the product through the five senses, such as the type/variant and packaging of coffee in a coffee-to-go shop that attracts customers' attention.
- Perceived quality, namely the image and reputation of the product as perceived by consumers, such as service, type / variety, and quality of coffee at coffee-to-go shops that can be felt by customers.

According to Abubakar et al. (2016), *E-WOM* is the value that consumers want to share regarding their opinions about bad and good experiences with a product that can be shared on the internet and can be seen by millions of people in the world.

B. Electronic Word of Mouth

According to Goyette (2010) *E-WOM* has three dimensions, namely:

- *Intensity is the number of comments written by consumers on a site (Liu, 2006). Intensity consists of the following indicators:*

- Frequency of *coffee-to-go shop* customers accessing information from the internet
- Frequency of *coffee-to-go shop* interaction with internet users
- The number of reviews written by *coffee-to-go shop* customers via the internet

➤ *Valence of Opinion includes:*

- Positive comments from *coffee-to-go shop* customers on the internet
- Recommendations from *coffee-to-go shop* customers on the internet

➤ *Content is the content of information from the internet related to products and services. Content information indicators include:*

- Variety of drinks and food at *coffee-to-go shops*
- Coffee quality at *coffee-to-go shops*
- Drink and food prices at *coffee-to-go shops*

➤ *Brand Image*

According to Lestyowati (2019), *brand image* plays an important role in the development of a brand because it involves the reputation and credibility of the brand which then becomes a guide for the consumer audience to try or use a product or service.

- *In brand image, there are three dimensions, including (Saputri & Guritno, 2021):*
- ✓ Brand Strength is the strength of the brand where how often information about the brand enters the consumer's memory and is managed by the sensory part of the brain as part of the brand image.
- ✓ Brand Favorability is the consumer's preference for the brand, forming consumer trust by providing attributes and benefits of how what is provided by a brand can satisfy the needs and desires of consumers so as to create a positive attitude towards the brand.
- ✓ Brand uniqueness is making a unique impression and a meaningful difference among other brands and making consumers have no reason not to own the brand.

➤ *Perceived Customer Value*

According to Ryu, et al. (2011), customer perceived value can be defined as the result of a personal comparison between the perceived overall benefit and the perceived sacrifice or cost paid by the customer for a good or service. According to Sweeney and Soutar (2001), there are four dimensions of *customer perceived value*, namely:

- Emotional value is the benefit derived from the feelings or affective statements generated by *coffee* at *coffee-to-go shops*.
- Social value is the benefit gained from *coffee* at *coffee-to-go shops* to improve social self-concept.

- Value for money is the benefit derived from *coffee* at a *coffee-to-go shop* with regard to short-term and long-term cost reduction.
- Performance functional value is the benefit derived from the perceived quality and expected performance of *coffee* at a *coffee-to-go shop*.

C. *Customer Satisfaction*

Satisfaction is a feeling that arises in a person, whether happy or disappointed when comparing the results of product performance with his expectations. According to Lovelock and Wirtz (2016), customer satisfaction provides many benefits for companies including:

- Isolate customers from competition
- Can create sustainable excellence
- Reduce the cost of failure
- Encouraging return customers
- Drive customer loyalty
- Promote positive word-of-mouth
- Lower costs to attract new customers

• *Repurchase Interest*

According to Charo et al. (2015), purchase intention is user behavior where buyers have a strong willingness to choose, pay, use, or consume products or services offered by a company. According to Basrah & Samsul (2012), there are four dimensions of Repurchase Intention, namely:

- ✓ Transactional Interest; The tendency of *coffee-to-go shop* customers to always repurchase
- ✓ Referential Interest; The willingness of *coffee-to-go shop* customers to recommend products they have consumed to others.
- ✓ Preferential Interest; The behavior of *coffee-to-go shop* customers who make the *coffee-to-go shop coffee* they have consumed their first choice.
- ✓ Explorative Interest; The desire of *coffee-to-go shop* customers to always seek information about *coffee-to-go shop coffee* that they are interested in.

III. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This study uses a *single cross-sectional design* to collect data from each element of the population and is conducted only once in one research period. The population in this study is generation Y and Z in DKI Jakarta because DKI Jakarta is the city with the most coffee shops. Based on data from the Central Statistics Agency (2021), the population of generation Y is 2,671,104 people and generation Z is 2,518,762 people. So that the total population reaches 5,189,866 people. There are 29 indicators in this study, so the sample size of this study is: $5 \times 29 = 145$ respondents So, the sample size for this study was 145 respondents for Gen Y and 145 respondents for Gen Z.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

A. Descriptive Statistics

Based on the questionnaires distributed to the respondents who have been determined, information regarding the characteristics of the respondents from each group is obtained as described in the following table:

Table 4 Respondent Characteristics Gen Y

Characteristics	Total	Percentage	
Age	25-30	29	20%
	31-35	91	62,75%
	36-40	25	17,25%
	Total	145	100%
Education	SMP	1	0,68%
	HIGH SCHOOL	12	8,28%
	S1	109	75,18%
	S2	23	15,86%
	Total	145	100%
Expenses per month	< Rp. 2.5 Jt	4	2,7%
	Rp. 2.5 Jt - Rp. 7.5 Jt	38	26,2%
	Rp. 7.5 Jt - Rp. 12.5 Jt	50	34,6%
	> Rp. 12.5 Jt	53	36,5%
	Total	145	100%
Purchase Frequency per month	1-3 times	66	45,52%
	4-6 times	38	26,2%
	7-10 times	29	20%
	> 10 times	12	8,28%
	Total	145	100%

Source: Questionnaire (2023)

Then for respondents who come from generation Z, their characteristics can be described in the following table:

Table 5 Respondent Characteristics Gen Z

Characteristics	Total	Percentage	
Age	20-22	58	40%
	23-24	87	60%
	Total	145	100%
Education	HIGH SCHOOL	53	36,55%
	S1	87	60,00%
	S2	4	2,76%
	S3	1	0,69%
	Total	145	100%
Expenses per month	< Rp. 2.5 million	33	22,76%
	IDR 2.5 million - IDR 7.5 million	69	47,59%
	IDR 7.5 million - IDR 12.5 million	36	24,83%

Source: Questionnaire (2023)

B. Outer Model Evaluation Results

➤ *Convergent Validity*

To test convergent validity, the outer loading value or loading factor is used. An indicator is declared to meet convergent validity in a good category if the outer loading value is > 0.7.

Fig 4 Outer Model
Source: Smart PLS Processing Results (2023)

The following is the *outer loading* value of each research variable statement item:

Table 6 Outer Loading

Variables	Indicator	Outer Loading	Validity
Product and Service Quality (X1)	X1.1	0,734	Valid
	X1.2	0.711	Valid
	X1.3	0.689	Valid
	X1.4	0.711	Valid
	X1.5	0.715	Valid
	X1.6	0.694	Valid
	X1.7	0.707	Valid
	X1.8	0.685	Valid
	X1.9	0.719	Valid
	X1.10	0.730	Valid
	X1.11	0.731	Valid
	X1.12	0.707	Valid
	X1.13	0.705	Valid
Electronic word of mouth (X2)	X2.1	0.869	Valid
	X2.2	0.821	Valid
	X2.3	0.835	Valid
Brand Image (X3)	X3.1	0.836	Valid
	X3.2	0.817	Valid
	X3.3	0.795	Valid

Perceived Customer Value (X4)	X4.1	0.764	Valid
	X4.2	0.830	Valid
	X4.3	0.862	Valid
	X4.4	0.813	Valid
Customer satisfaction (Z)	Z.1	0.910	Valid
	Z.2	0.903	Valid
Repurchase intention (Y)	Y.1	0.882	Valid
	Y.2	0.897	Valid
	Y.3	0.883	Valid
	Y.4	0.752	Valid

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2022

All indicators are declared feasible or valid for research use and can be used for further analysis.

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

Table 7 Average Variant Extracted (AVE)

Variables	AVE	Validity
Product and service quality	0,505	Valid
<i>Electronic word of mouth</i>	0,709	Valid
Brand Image	0,666	Valid
Perceived Customer Value	0,669	Valid
Customer satisfaction	0,822	Valid
Repurchase intention	0,732	Valid

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2023

Based on table 4.4 above, it is known that the AVE value of product and service quality variables, *electronic word of mouth*, brand image, perceived customer value, customer satisfaction and repurchase interest > 0.5. Thus it can be stated that each variable has good *discriminant validity*. The following is the *composite reliability* value of each research variable:

➤ *Discriminant Validity*

Table 8 Composite Reliability

Variables	Composite Reliability	Reliability
Product and service quality	0,930	Reliable
Electronic word of mouth	0,880	Reliable
Brand Image	0,857	Reliable
Perceived Customer Value	0,890	Reliable
Customer satisfaction	0,902	Reliable
Repurchase intention	0,916	Reliable

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2022

≥Based on table 4.4 above, it can be seen that the *composite reliability* value obtained on all research variables is 0.7. These results indicate that each variable has met the *composite reliability* so that it can be concluded that all variables are reliable with a high level. The following is the *Cronbach alpha* value of each variable:

Table 9 Cronbach Alpha

Variables	Cronbach Alpha	Reliability
Product And Service Quality	0,918	Reliable
Electronic Word Of Mouth	0,794	Reliable
Brand Image	0,750	Reliable
Perceived Customer Value	0,835	Reliable
Customer Satisfaction	0,783	Reliable
Repurchase Intention	0,876	Reliable

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2022

Based on table 4.5, it can be seen that the *Cronbach alpha* value of each research variable is 0.7. Thus these results indicate that each research variable has met the requirements for the *Cronbach alpha* value, so it can be concluded that all variables have a high level of reliability.

C. Inner Model Evaluation Results

Fig 5 Inner Model (Boot Strapping)

Based on the *outer model* scheme that has been displayed in the figure above, it can be explained that the *path coefficient* value on the dominant *path coefficient* is shown in the customer satisfaction variable on repurchase interest of 0.752. Then the second path coefficient is shown in the brand image variable on repurchase interest of 0.265. While the smallest value is shown in the variable perceived customer value on customer satisfaction of 0.192.

Based on the *inner model* scheme that has been displayed in Figure 4.2 above, it can be explained that the largest t-statistic value is shown by customer satisfaction on repurchase interest of 22.640. Then the second largest influence is the effect of brand image on customer satisfaction of 3.490. While the smallest influence is shown in the *electronic word of mouth* variable on customer satisfaction of 1.980.

Based on the description of these results, it shows that the independent variables on customer satisfaction in this model have a *path coefficient* value with a positive number. This shows that if the greater the *path coefficient* value in one of the independent variables on the customer satisfaction variable, the stronger the influence between the independent variables on the customer satisfaction variable. Meanwhile, the independent variable on repurchase intention in this model has a *path coefficient* value with a positive number. This shows that if the greater the *path coefficient* value on one of the independent variables on the repurchase interest variable, the stronger the influence between the independent variables on the repurchase interest variable.

Table 10 R-Square Value

Variables	R Square Value
Customer satisfaction	0,603
Repurchase intention	0,566

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2023

Based on the data in table 4.6 above, it can be seen that the *R-Square* value for the customer satisfaction variable is 0.603. This value explains that customer satisfaction can be explained by the variables of product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth*, brand image and perceived customer value by 60.3%, while the remaining 39.7% can be influenced by other variables not examined. Then for the repurchase interest variable, it has an R-Square value of 0.566. This value explains that repurchase interest can be explained by the customer satisfaction variable by 56.6% while the remaining 43.4% can be influenced by other variables not studied.

The goodness of fit assessment is known from the Q-Square value. The Q-Square value has the same

➤ *Hypothesis Test*

meaning as the coefficient of determination (R-Square) in regression analysis, where the higher the Q-Square, the better or more fit the model is with the data. The results of the calculation of the Q-Square value are as follows:

$$Q\text{-Square} = 1 - [(1 - R^2 \text{ 1}) \times (1 - R \text{ 2})]^2 = 1 - [(1 - 0,603) \times (1 - 0,566)] = 1 - (0,397 \times 0,434) = 1 - 0,172 = 0,828$$

Based on the results of the above calculations, the Q-Square value is 0.828. This shows that the amount of diversity of research data that can be explained by the research model is 82.8%. Thus, from these results, this research model can be declared to have good goodness of fit.

Table 11 Direct Effect

Hypothesis	Influence	Original Sample	T- Statistic	P- Values	Results
H1	Product and service quality => Customer satisfaction	0,211	2,087	0,037	Accepted
H2	<i>Electronic word of mouth</i> => Customer satisfaction	0,196	1,980	0,048	Accepted
H3	Brand image => Customer satisfaction	0,265	3,490	0,001	Accepted
H4	Perceived customer value => Customer satisfaction	0,192	2,523	0,012	Accepted
H5	Customer satisfaction => Repurchase intention	0,752	22,640	0,000	Accepted

Source: PLS Results, 2023

Based on the table above, it can be seen that the product and service quality variable has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of 2.087 > 1.96. The *electronic word of mouth* variable has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of 1.980 > 1.96. The brand image variable has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction of 3.490 > 1.96. The variable perceived customer value has a positive and significant effect on customer satisfaction by 2.523 > 1.96. The customer satisfaction variable has a positive and significant effect on repurchase intention of 22.640 > 1.96.

Table 12 PLS Multigroup Analysis Test Results for Groups Generation Y and Generation Z

Influence between Variables	Path Coefficients-diff (Generation Y – Generation Z)	1-tailed original p- Value (Generation Y vs Generation Z)	P-Value new (Generation Y vs Generation Z)
Brand Image -> Customer Satisfaction	0.016	0.461	0.922
E-WOM -> Customer Satisfaction	0.253	0.091	0.182
Customer Satisfaction -> Repurchase Interest	0.020	0.367	0.735
Product and Service Quality -> Customer Satisfaction	-0.303	0.947	0.105
Perceived Customer Value -> Customer Satisfaction	0.006	0.482	0.963

Source: PLS Processing Results, 2023

Based on table 4.10, it can be seen that the P value for generation Y and Generation Z has a value greater than 0.05, which indicates that the influence between product and service quality, electronic word of mouth, brand image and perceived customer value on customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction on repurchase interest there is no significant difference between generation Y and generation Z.

V. CLOSING

➤ Conclusion

Based on the findings of the research on repurchase interest and the factors that influence it and the explanation in the previous chapters, several research conclusions can be stated as follows:

- There is a positive and significant effect of product and service quality on customer satisfaction (generation Y and Z) *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- There is a positive and significant effect of *electronic word of mouth* on customer satisfaction (generation Y and Z) *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- There is a positive and significant effect of brand image on customer satisfaction (generation Y and Z) *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- There is a positive and significant effect of perceived customer value on customer satisfaction (generation Y and Z) *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- There is a positive and significant effect of customer satisfaction on repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To Go Shop*.
- Customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between product and service quality and repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- Customer satisfaction cannot mediate the relationship between *electronic word of mouth* and repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- Customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between brand image and repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- Customer satisfaction can mediate the relationship between perceived customer value and repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*.
- There is no significant difference between Generation Y and Generation Z regarding the influence between product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth*, brand image and perceived customer value on customer satisfaction and customer satisfaction on repurchase intention.

➤ Advice

Based on the conclusions of the research results, several suggestions can be put forward which are expected to be useful as follows:

- Product and service quality is proven to have a significant and positive effect on customer satisfaction in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*. For this reason, it is recommended to maintain and further improve the quality of existing products and services.
- *Electronic word of mouth* is proven to have a significant and positive effect on repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*. For this reason, it is recommended to maintain and further improve *electronic word of mouth* with efforts to increase more accurate information about product

and service quality.

- Brand image is proven to have a significant and positive effect on repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*. For this reason, it is recommended to maintain and further improve the brand image by trying to improve the image of the *Coffee-To-Go Shop* so that it is more firmly embedded in the minds of customers.
- Perceived customer value can have a significant and positive effect on repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*. For this reason, it is recommended to maintain and further improve the perception of customer value.
- Customer satisfaction is proven to have a significant and positive effect on repurchase intention in generation Y and Z *Coffee-To-Go Shop*. For this reason, it is recommended to increase customer satisfaction by improving product and service quality, *electronic word of mouth*, brand image and perceived customer value.
- For other researchers who will conduct research with similar themes, it is hoped that they can add several variables that can affect customer satisfaction and repurchase interest and can expand the research object not only limited to *Coffee-To-Go Shop*, in order to obtain maximum results.

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